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Five-Phase Synchronous Machine Design Using Numerical MAXWELL Software

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Abstract – The study of the electromagnetic case is important in electric machine, especially in the field of design, we will learn how to make a model of three phase synchronous machine and five phase synchronous machine. The geometry model is designed in the RMXprt file, and the electromagnetic simulation in MAXWELL simulator. In solving electromagnetic equations, the Finite Element Method (FEM) was relied upon, which allows partitioning the solution space and solving it directly. The temperature path, magnetic field density, flux line and induced voltage of the two machines were tracked in MAXWELL software to show how the machine works. The speed and torque curve for different times during machine operation are also shown. The distribution of electromagnetic fields between the stator and the rotor shows us the work of a five-phase synchronous machine and the difference between it and a three-phase synchronous machine. From the results extracted from the design, it is clear that the five-phase synchronous machine design is more robust in work.

Keywords – *Five-Phase Synchronous Machine, Ansys Maxwell; the magnetic field, Finite Element Method*

I. INTRODUCTION

Electric motors are used to convert electrical energy into mechanical energy, one of these motors is the synchronous machine [1], ing Zhao et al [2][11] Work was carried out on a five-phase machine to investigate electromagnetism, Yemna Bensalem et Mohamed Naceur Abdelkrim [3] study Induction Motor based on Finite Element Analysis, Ashish Nigam and Subhan Siddiqui [4] investigated Modeling and Simulation of Five Phase Synchronous Motor.

In this study we will design and perform an electromagnetic simulation on a synchronous machine using ANSYS. The three-phase synchronous machine was designed in RMXprt, and

the electromagnetic simulation in MAXWELL, and based on the results, the five-phase synchronous machine was designed, Solving electromagnetic equations requires using finite element method, we trace the flux path and electromagnetism in machine parts.

II. GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Determining magnetic fields is of great importance in the field of designing electric motors, where partial differential equations are converted into algebraic equations that provide determining the distribution of fields [3]. This method is the finite element method.

Finite element technology analyzes irregular structures and complex shapes in a synchronous

motor where the solution network can be modified and applied precisely. The most important equations related to the magnetic field in Maxwell [5-6]

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J} \\ \mu \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B} = \nabla \times \mathbf{A} \\ \nabla \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{A}) = \mu \mathbf{J} \end{array} \right. \quad (1)$$

Where B is the magnetic flux, H is the magnetic field, J is the applied current, μ permeability of the magnetic material.

III. MODELING DESIGN

To create the three or five phase synchronous machine, we use Ansys RMXprt, which allows us to prepare the engineering of electrical machines, as it shows the principle of operation and performance with the extraction of simulation result, to design a highly efficient model the following elements should be considered for stator and rotor windings and poles of stator [7] In this work, a synchronous machine was designed and the characteristics of the motor were studied. Some parameter and characteristic values are given for both rotor and stator.

Table 1 Specifications of the stator

Stator				
Name	Value	Unit	Evaluated Value	
Outer Diameter	300	mm	300mm	
Inner Diameter	211	mm	211mm	
Length	75	mm	75mm	
Stacking Factor	0.95			
Steel Type	M27_29G			
Number of Slots	18			
Slot Type	4			
Skew Width	0		0	

Table 2 Specifications of the Rotor

Rotor				
Name	Value	Unit	Evaluated Value	
Outer Diameter	210	mm	210mm	
Inner Diameter	145	mm	145mm	
Length	65	mm	65mm	
Steel Type	M27_29G			
Stacking Factor	0.95			
Pole Type	5			

The number of slots in the stator is 18 to determine the three windings that represent the phases. Each phase has 6 slots.

From the design in RMXprt Figure 1 we can get the design automatically in Maxwell Fig 2

Fig .1. synchronous machine in RMXprt

Fig.2.synchronous machine in Maxwell

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Three phase synchronous machine

The fig 4 shows the temperature distribution in the machine, the fig 3 shows the distribution of the magnetic flux density in the different parts of the machine.

Fig.3. magnetic flux density

Fig.4. Temperature

Fluctuation in torque value between 4 and -10 in fig 5, The speed remains constant for the duration of the operation of the engine 1500 rpm in fig 6.

Fig.5. torque curve

Fig.6. Speed curve

B. Five phase synchronous machine

In this part, we will design a five-phase synchronous machine in Ansys Maxwell, taking into account the appropriate dimensions of the rotor and stator parts as well as changing the electromagnetic fields during operation to match the design.

Table 3. Specifications of the stator

Name	Value	Unit	Evaluated Value	Description
Command	Create Use...			
Coordinate Sys...	Global			
DLL Name	RMxprt/SL...			
DLL Location	syslib			
DLL Version	12.1			
Diagap	211	mm	211mm	Core diameter on gap
Diayoke	300	mm	300mm	Core diameter on yoke
Length	0	mm	0mm	Core length
Skew	0	deg	0deg	Skew angle in core len
Slots	40		40	Number of slots
SlotType	4		4	Slot type: 1 to 6
Hs0	2	mm	2mm	Slot opening height
Hs01	0	mm	0mm	Slot closed bridge heig
Hs1	1	mm	1mm	Slot wedge height
Hs2	17	mm	17mm	Slot body height
Bs0	4	mm	4mm	Slot opening width
Bs1	7	mm	7mm	Slot wedge maximum v
Bs2	14	mm	14mm	Slot body bottom width
Rf	0	mm	0mm	Slot body bottom fillet
FillType	0		0	0: a quarter circle; 1: to
Half Slot	0		0	0 for symmetric slot, 1 f
SegAngle	15	deg	15deg	Deviation angle for slot
LenRegion	0	mm	0mm	Region length

Table 4. Specifications of the Rotor

Name	Value	Unit	Evaluated Value	Description
Command	Create User Defined Part			
Coordinate Sys...	Global			
DLL Name	RMxprt/IFMCore			
DLL Location	syslib			
DLL Version	15.0			
Diagap	210	mm	210mm	Core diameter on gap s...
Diayoke	145	mm	145mm	Core diameter on yoke
Length	0	mm	0mm	Core length
Poles	20		20	Number of poles
PoleType	5		5	Pole type: 1 to 6
D1	206	mm	206mm	Limited diameter of PM
O1	0	mm	0mm	Bottom width for separa...
O2	20.182485374512	mm	20.1824853745...	Distance from duct bott...
B1	10	mm	10mm	Duct thickness
Rib	10	mm	10mm	Rib width
IRib	9.8327071854659	mm	9.83270718546...	Rib height (for types 3-5)
DminMag	0	mm	0mm	Minimum distance betw...
ThickMag	10	mm	10mm	Magnet thickness
WidthMag	1	mm	1mm	Total width of all magn...
LenRegion	0	mm	0mm	Region length
InfoCore	0		0	0: core; 1: magnets; 2...

40 slots are required in the stator to make the five-phase machine each phase has 8 slots, Five phases of the same wave and between phase and phase $2\pi/5$ degree.[8][9]:

$$v_a(t) = 220 * \sin(2 . \pi . f . t)$$

$$v_b(t) = 220 * \sin(2 . \pi . f . t - 2\pi/5)$$

$$v_c(t) = 220 * \sin(2 . \pi . f . t - 4\pi/5)$$

$$v_d(t) = 220 * \sin(2 . \pi . f . t + 4\pi/5)$$

$$v_e(t) = 220 * \sin(2 . \pi . f . t + 2\pi/5)$$

The work of the machine depends on a precise arrangement of the stator slots according to the signal of the five phases [10].

TABLE 5 five winding of ABCDE

Slots	Phase	Slots	Phase	Slots	Phase	Slots	Phase
1	A +	6	A+	11	A -	16	A -
2	C -	7	C -	12	C +	17	C +
3	E +	8	E +	13	E -	18	E -
4	B -	9	B -	14	B +	19	B +
5	D +	10	D +	15	D -	20	D -

Fig .7. Five phase synchronous machine

Fig 8 shows the temperatures in the synchronous machine, as it appears that the temperature is high between the slot of the stator and the rotor.

Fig.8. temperature

Fig 9 shows the flux line distribution in the machine parts and the largest values at the level of the stator teeth and the rotor. This flow is due to the work of each phase.

Fig.9.flux line

Fig 10 shows the transfer of the magnetic flux density from the phases of the stator to the rotor, and from here we conclude that the work of the rotor part depends on the magnetic flux density produced between the phases.

Fig.10. magnetic flux density

The work of the machine depends on the induced voltage in the stationary phases. Fig 11 shows five phases of the synchronous machine, A, B, C, D and E with an angle of $2\pi/5$ degrees between them.

Fig.11. induced voltage

An increase in the torque value at the start of the machine, and then the value returns to 0, and this is one of the advantages of the five-phase machine in Fig 12. But the speed is constant in Fig 13.

Fig.12. torque curve

Fig.13. Speed curve

V. CONCLUSION

The Ansys program is characterized by the precision of the design of the various parts of the engine, including the visualization of the magnetic fields of the electric machine.

The five-phase synchronous machine is designed in Ansys Maxwell, with determination of the stator and rotating part values of the machine.

The simulation results are extracted, which are torque, speed, flux, and induced voltage, The magnetic flux and temperature are also observed in the synchronous machine.

The method used to calculate the results is FEM which is almost Perfect.

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